

Idealized Spatial Probability for Mixed Momenta

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In the literature (1), a classical spatial density seems to be based on the amount of time a particle spends in a region dx . Thus: Probability is proportional to $dt = dx/v(x)$. With a normalization constant, one has: $P(x)dx = Cdx/v(x)$. For constant $v(x)$ values, one has the same probability function for different v . If one has a problem in which there may be either one v_1 constant or v_2 constant, and wishes to create an idealized distribution (not one based on independent appearances of v_1 or v_2 at different x values), then it seems one may expect a v_1 at dx at x_1 and then v_2 at x_1+dx if the probabilities for v_1 and v_2 are the same.. We call this an idealized distribution because it is like considering heads at t_1 then tails at t_2 , heads at t_3 etc. In such a case, there would be a periodic probability because even if v_1 and v_2 have the same weight, Δt is different for each in dx .

As a result, we argue that even classically the possibility of having two different constant velocities, or momenta if one wishes to use a variable which is linked on impulse and does not require a clock for measurement, one might expect an oscillatory spatial density even though each p is linked with a constant density in space, i.e. $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length. To create such a density, we suggest that one use the variable p_1-p_2 (one dimension) as the argument of the periodic function, because the periodicity disappears if $p_1=p_2$.

It turns out that such a scheme is linked to the problem of finding a probability $F(p,x)$ which leads to conservation of momentum (2). It was found that if one has $F(p_1,x)F(p_2,x)=F(p_1+p_2,x)$ (one dimension) one must introduce a second variable x and create orthogonal functions in x to force probability to be 0 if momenta does not match. If momenta match, then one has a constant, i.e. no equal crests and troughs in space. This scenario however, requires using $-p_3-p_4$ for final momenta and p_1+p_2 for initial and leads to $F(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$. If this is the case, then $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ should be interpreted as a particle with p at x and the probability of its time reversed state (i.e. the state which starts at $t+dt$) being linked to p . Then the product yields 1 and one has equal weights for all x . If one has p_1 and p_2 however, a probability to have p_1 at x may have a p_2 at $t+dt$ and then a p_1 at t .

We consider the p_1, p_2 case of $\exp(ip_1x)+\exp(ip_2x)$ and see that one obtains a real, periodic plus constant spatial density, but that average momentum has a complex piece. We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is complex because it is associated with motion in one direction. If one takes an expectation value of a real variable, say p (or $pp/2m$), with a complex flow probability, then one may obtain complex terms because the case of $-p_1, -p_2$ leads to a complex term with the opposite sign. Thus, the complex number nature seems to be linked to the flow probability $\exp(ipx)$ which is direction sensitive.

Classical Spatial Density

In (1) and elsewhere it is suggested that a spatial classical probability is proportional to the amount of time a particle spends in each dx . Then:

$$P(x)dx = Cdx/v(x) \quad \text{where } .5mv(x)v(x) + V(x)=E \quad ((1)) \quad (\text{nonrelativstically})$$

If $v(x)=\text{constant}$, the same distribution holds for all v values. What happens if there is a probability to have v_1 and another to have v_2 ? In such case, dt_1 and dt_2 are not the same at each x . One could try to model this like the toss of die, in which case there exists a certain probability to have heads at t_1 etc, but one may also create an idealized probability. If heads = .5 and tails = .5, an idealized probability would have heads followed by tails then by heads etc. If this same strategy is applied to the v_1, v_2 case, one would expect an oscillating probability in x , with a high peak for a low velocity and a low peak for a high velocity, if probability is taken to be proportional to dt .

We do not wish to consider a probability proportional to dt , but wish to work with momenta which are measured by impulse which does not require a clock. Furthermore, we wish to have oscillatory behaviour disappear if $p_1=p_2$.

Momentum Spatial Probability Scheme

As noted above, we suggest a spatial probability distribution based on momentum which does not require a clock. If one keeps this notion of no clock present, one does not follow a particle in time, but describes space by probability based on x, p . It seems this implies the particle's past, present and future are placed together along x .

If one has two particles with p_1 and p_2 and there is no time in the picture, one might have p_1 at or p_2 at x . We suggest that the oscillatory scenario described above should hold, but we argue that the periodic term should be a function of $(p_1-p_2)x$ so that if $p_1-p_2=0$, this term disappears. If one uses cosine as the periodicity function, then:

$$P(x)dx = dx (1 + \cos(p_1-p_2)x) \quad ((2))$$

This is an idealized probability, one based on tossing a die to see which p is at x . If one integrates over x , then it is as if the periodic term is not present, it integrates to 0, but it does contribute to $P(x)$.

In (2), we argued that one may obtain the quantum free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, by seeking a probability $F(p,x)$ which leads to conservation of momentum. The first step was to argue that $F(p_1,x)F(p_2,x)=F(p_1+p_2,x)$ one dimension. It was then necessary to argue that one use $-p_3-p_4$ for a later time and p_1+p_2 for an earlier time so that in the case of momentum conservation all periodicity vanishes and one has a constant. This means that periodicity, i.e. equal crests/troughs, is equivalent to orthogonal functions.

We note that the probability $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with conservation of momentum in the following way:

A single particle has a constant momentum p . If it has a probability $F(p,x)$ this does not indicate that p is conserved in time. We argue that one wishes to compare p at t and p at $t+dt$. The above rule was to use $-p$ for $t+dt$ (i.e. the time reversed state) so that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ which indicates no preference of x . This conclusion, however, is based on momentum conservation, not equal amount of time dt at each dx .

This idea seems to suggest that there may be periodicity of spatial density if one has p_1 and p_2 , because one may have $\exp(ip_1x)$ at t and $\exp(-ip_2x)$ at $t+dt$. In other words:

$$(\exp(-ip_2x)+\exp(-ip_1x)) (\exp(ip_1x) + \exp(ip_2x)) = 2 + 2 \cos((p_1-p_2)x) \quad ((3))$$

If $p_1-p_2=0$, the periodicity disappears and so one has the kind of idealized oscillatory spatial probability function suggested above, but this time it is obtained using a probability function which conserves momentum.

Average Momentum in the Idealized Probability Scheme

Momentum (one dimension) is a real number, but $\exp(ipx)$ is not. It is complex, and the complex number nature is associated with the direction of p in space. If one a single p , then:

$$\exp(-ipx) p \exp(ipx) = p = \text{real number} \quad ((4))$$

If one, however, has p_1 at x and then at $t+dt$, p_2 , one has an overall probability flux density in the positive direction for $p_1 > p_2$. One would then not necessarily expect the average p to be a real number, even though p is. There should, however, be a connection with an expression for $-p_1, -p_2$.

First, average p is:

$$(\exp(-ip_2x)+\exp(-ip_1x)) (p_1 \exp(ip_1x) + p_2 \exp(ip_2x)) = p_1 + p_2 + (p_1+p_2) \cos((p_1-p_2)x) + (p_1-p_2) i \sin((p_1-p_2)x) \quad ((5))$$

If $p_1=p_2$, both the real and imaginary oscillatory pieces are not oscillatory. One has an imaginary average momentum piece, but if one considers ((5)) for $p_1 \rightarrow -p_1$ and $p_2 \rightarrow -p_2$, then adding the two expressions yields:

$$2 (p_1-p_2) i \sin((p_1-p_2)x) \quad ((6))$$

This suggests an oscillatory average momentum which is in common for p_1 , p_2 and $-p_1, -p_2$. This is like $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ having $\cos(px)$ in common.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that using dt as proportional to $P(x)dx = Cdx/v(x)$, where $v(x)=\text{velocity}$, suggests an idealized oscillatory probability if one has two constant velocities, v_1 and v_2 , because these have different dt values for a constant dx . An idealized probability here suggests v_1 at one x and the v_2 at another etc.

We next wish to consider the variable momentum which is measured by impulse and does not require a clock. We wish to have a p_1 and p_2 and distribution in space. We suggest that one

should still have an oscillatory result, but the oscillating function should be $\cos((p_1-p_2)x)$ so that if $p_1=p_2$, there is no oscillation.

We argue that this result is consistent with a scheme (2) to create a probability which conserves momentum. This scheme required that one use $-p_3-p_4$ for $t+dt$ and p_1+p_2 for t . In other words, conservation occurs from one t to another. The probability function found was $\exp(ipx)$. For a single particle, this suggests conservation of momentum: $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$, or no preference in space. If, however, one may have p_1 or p_2 , then one may have p_1 at t and $-p_2$ at $t+dt$. This leads to: $(\exp(-ip_1x)+\exp(-ip_2x))(\exp(ip_1x)+\exp(ip_2x))$ which yields the same kind of oscillatory density.

We also consider the case of average p , which brings in an imaginary oscillatory term. This comes from the complex flow probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ used and shows that there is a common oscillatory piece for both p_1, p_2 and $-p_1, -p_2$, just as $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ have $\cos(px)$ in common.

References

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